

SUSTAINABLE SPATIAL TRANSFORMATION OF THE INNOVATION AND TRAINING PARK (ITP) PRIZREN

Towards a hub for innovation, economic
development and digital transformation

SUSTAINABLE SPATIAL TRANSFORMATION OF THE INNOVATION AND TRAINING PARK (ITP) PRIZREN: TOWARDS A HUB FOR INNOVATION, ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT AND DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION

STUDY

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FOREWORD

This urban design study was conducted by Octagon Architekturbüro and provides a strategy for the sustainable spatial transformation of the Innovation and Training Park (ITP) Prizren, Kosovo in order to create a hub for innovation, economic development and digital transformation in the city and the wider region.

According to the quadruple helix model for innovation (Carayannis & Campbell, 2009), an innovation ecosystem requires that actors from different societal spheres come together to collaborate with each other, namely from academia, civil society, government and the private sector. If we apply this concept on a spatial level, this means we need spaces for collaboration of those actors. If there are no spaces for encounters, there will be no opportunity for collaboration and thus no innovation ecosystem can be established. What sounds like a simple exercise is in fact a major challenge in contemporary urban design.

In the case of the Innovation and Training Park (ITP) Prizren, situated on the grounds of a former Kosovo Force (KFOR) military camp, the challenge is to take a space not created for innovation nor public accessibility and transform it sustainably into an open space that can facilitate this socio-economic interaction. To this end, the present study investigates the ITP's spatial potential and possibilities for how the park can be redeveloped by transforming the existing infrastructure and increasing its accessibility.

In order to gain a better understanding of the different needs and requirements of current and future tenants as well as potential park users, this urban design study was conducted alongside two participatory events; a multi-stakeholder dialogue and a public consultation. A broader participatory process should ideally accompany the future development of the ITP.

This study as well as the participatory events were conducted as part of the research project Sustainability, Entrepreneurship and Global Digital Transformation (SET) at the Alexander von Humboldt Institute for Internet and Society (HIIG). The project was funded by the Deutsche Gesellschaft für internationale Zusammenarbeit (GIZ) on behalf of the German Federal Ministry for Economic Cooperation and Development (BMZ). We would like to thank the ITP and the Digital Transformation Center Kosovo for the kind cooperation and facilitation of this study.

Christian Grauvogel, Head of Dialogue and Knowledge Transfer, HIIG

**THE CHALLENGE IS TO TAKE A SPACE
NOT CREATED FOR INNOVATION
NOR PUBLIC ACCESSIBILITY AND
TRANSFORM IT SUSTAINABLY INTO AN
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SOCIO-ECONOMIC INTERACTION**

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INTRODUCTION

This study proposes an urban design strategy for the sustainable spatial transformation of the Innovation and Training Park (ITP) Prizren. The ITP is located on a former military camp that has undergone a transition to civilian use starting in 2018. This transformation raises questions about future utilisation, public accessibility and the significance of the ITP for the entire city and region.

The ITP's management and consortium envision the park as a campus for education and research, ICT and technology companies, as well as cultural and creative industries – altogether creating a unique innovation ecosystem. In the first years of development, the pioneer tenants moved into the park, using the existing building structures for their needs. However, an overall planning and architectural strategy for the park, as well as its implementation, is still in progress.

In order to develop an urban design strategy for the ITP, this study provides an analysis of the given spatial conditions. In addition, it includes the results of discussions with stakeholders from two participatory events. Taking into account the potentials and deficits of the site, initial planning priorities (accessibility, programming and climate) were developed, which led to an overall spatial concept for the ITP.

**THE STUDY AT HAND SUGGESTS A
FRAMEWORK FOR FURTHER DETAILED
PLANNING AND A STRATEGIC ROADMAP
FOR THE DEVELOPMENT PROCESS**

The study at hand suggests a framework for further detailed planning and a strategic roadmap for the development process. The focus is on a user- and process-oriented approach, which also includes temporary and cost-effective measures that enable direct implementation. In addition, the detailed design of two key areas, the entrance and the central square of the ITP serve as a showcase for the overall approach.

N.B. The spatial analyses are from the period May 2022 – October 2022, therefore some of the descriptions might be outdated by current measures and developments.

SPATIAL SURVEY

PAST, PRESENT AND FUTURE

The former Kosovo Force (KFOR) barracks in Prizren look back on a long history, mainly characterised by military use. The Ottoman army was stationed at the area for the first time in 1906¹, and later followed by Nazi-German, Italian² and then Yugoslavian military forces³. During the Kosovo war in 1999, a large part of the building structure was destroyed by NATO air strikes⁴. In the course of the KFOR mission, the barracks subsequently became a base of the German Armed Forces, which were stationed on site until 2018⁵.

Since then, many buildings on the site have remained empty, with currently only a few being used for various needs under the aegis of Innovation and Training Park (ITP) Prizren. However, plans to redevelop the entire area and to expand the ITP have been underway, led by Deutsche Gesellschaft für Internationale Zusammenarbeit (GIZ) in a joint venture with the Kosovar government.

Figure 1. Timeline

- <https://web.archive.org/web/20210919193254/https://itp-prizren.com/the-park/former-camp/>
- Jozo Tomasevich, War and Revolution in Yugoslavia, 1941-1945, Stanford, CA, 2002. ISBN 9780804779241
- <https://www.rycowb.org/?p=10491>
- Under orders: War crimes in Kosovo, in Human Rights Watch, 2001, 339.
- https://augengeradeaus.net/wp-content/uploads/2018/12/20181220_Kosovo_Schlie%C3%9Fung_Prizren.pdf

pic 05

AERIAL VIEW: LOCATION OF THE ITP

pic 06

pic 07

pic 08

pic 09

pic 10

pic 11

DEFICITS AND OPPORTUNITIES

The status quo of the ITP is currently still determined by a mixture of vacant or underused solitary buildings, sealed areas, undesigned green spaces and sports areas. The high level of surface sealing on the site in particular represents a deficit. Some of the sealed areas are used as car parks, but a large part lies fallow as a residue of old building structures. In addition, the park is difficult to access due to the continuous fencing and partitioning of the ITP area. This not only hinders physical accessibility to the park, but also gives the site an uninviting appearance. The same effect is delivered by closed and run-down facades of buildings within the park.

However existing infrastructures such as sports fields, vacant buildings and a road network offer promising opportunities. Many available elements can be activated in a low-threshold manner, which could boost the development of the ITP and positively contribute to the nearby neighbourhood. Current developments through pioneer users such as [Autostrada Biennale Hangar](#), the first and only contemporary art institution in Prizren, give an example of spatial and functional activation through artistic interventions and public engagements.

The spatial quality of the area results particularly from its unique geographic and topographic location as well as the existing green spaces. Most notably, the hillside location offers remarkable views of the city and the surrounding mountain landscape.

Figure 2. Deficits and opportunities

SPATIAL INVENTORY

Location and accessibility

Situated at the outskirts of the city of Prizren between its centre and the Šar Planina mountain range, the ITP enjoys an important location in terms of urban space. It lies near the city centre and benefits from good transport links via the National Motorway M25. At the same time, however, the M25 also acts as a barrier between the site and neighbourhoods to the west. There are no dedicated pedestrian crossings available over the highly frequented M25; a public bus line runs along the National Motorway towards the city centre.

The mobility structure of the area is mainly characterised by demarcation, with three major entrances to the area. Two of these are located to the west of the area on the M25, the third entrance is located slightly further south and is adjacent to a densely built residential area; secondary entrances are permanently closed. Possible pedestrian entrances from the residential area to the southwest of the park are currently limited due to the fencing. While the area currently functions as an office and production site with its first cultural venues, the ITP itself still has limited public access at the time of this inventory. The entrances are guarded by gatekeepers who control access to the area. Fencing isolates the ITP from the adjacent neighbourhood to the south as well as an open landscape to the east and an urbanised area to the west. Mobility on the site is currently focused on motorised transport, with car parks concentrated at the central area near the conference centre. It is still characterised by a roundabout connecting the entrance roads. Pedestrian accessibility is obstructed by poor quality of surfaces and steep paths.

Figure 3: Inventory of accessibility

Figure 4. Location

Built structure and programming

Due to the former long-term military use of the site, the existing built structure is very spartan and utilitarian. No continuous sequence of structures can be discerned on the site. Nevertheless, building types can be divided into clusters with certain characteristics.

The central area can be identified by larger standalone buildings such as the conference centre as well as small buildings that are used for overarching functions such as administration and service. To the north there is a cluster of old hangars and maintenance buildings. A smaller number of them are occupied by the cultural venue of Autostrada Biennale and smaller manufacturers. Directly adjacent are a sports field and two rows of former residential barracks. The barracks are currently underused and only little occupied, among others by the Makerspace Innovation Center. Other groups of smaller buildings are located to the southeast as well as to the west of the centre. The eastern area is much more spacious and less densely built. To the south of the sports field there is a cluster of former hospital buildings. The far south corner hosts a few standalone buildings and mostly green and wooded areas.

The buildings are of various states of maintenance; most of them are still unoccupied. The majority of the buildings that are already used are grouped towards the centre area, including the former canteen of the KFOR which is used as a conference centre.

Figure 5: Inventory of built structure

Landscape and nature

The most characteristic landscape element is the topography, which slopes southeast to northwest down from Šar Planina mountain ridge. This results in wide views over the city and the mountains in the central and southeast areas.

The landscape structure primarily consists of undesigned green areas and sealed concrete surfaces. Most of the sealed areas can be found in the northwest next to the hangars, as well as in the southeast next to the former hospital. The site has scarce vegetation throughout apart from the south, which has several relatively densely wooded areas.

Water disposal consists of a ditch system with narrow water channels distributed throughout the area, partly covered or tubed. A particular cluster of ditches emerges in the area of former helicopter landing pads along the M25, the natural low-lying site.

Figure 6: Inventory of landscape

SPATIAL ANALYSIS RESUME

Due to its long-standing use as military barracks, the site is characterised by a simple, specific functional organisation with low quality of spatial design and open spaces as well as poor climatic aspects. Nevertheless, other characteristics such as topography, low building density, existing larger buildings and the proximity to the city can be considered as assets.

In light of the likely future expansion of the city of Prizren and the construction developments on the hills of the Šar Planina, the ITP is expected to gain in importance. The key challenge is to develop the ITP as a hinge between urban and natural space by overcoming spatial and visual barriers. In this context, it is equally important to preserve the existing open space qualities and to strengthen public access to them.

Fig. 3 and Fig. 5 – Fig. 7 can be found in full size in the annex.

STAKEHOLDER DIALOGUE RESUME

In order to identify and better understand the specific needs and interests of current and potential user groups of the ITP, a multi-stakeholder dialogue was held on June 1, 2022. The stakeholder dialogue was organised and conceptualised by the Alexander von Humboldt Institute for Internet and Society (HIIG) and Octagon Architekturkollektiv in collaboration with the Innovation and Training Park (ITP) Prizren and the Digital Transformation Center Kosovo. Main intentions of the dialogue were to identify the area’s potential and its deficits and to develop initial spatial strategic approaches in order to foster the ITP ecosystem. A representative sample of local stakeholders, including current and possible future tenants as well as potential partners from the cultural sector, came together to exchange ideas during site visits, joint mapping and discursive multi-stakeholder dialogue formats.

The results of the workshop are largely in line with the findings from the preceding spatial analysis. These include a demand for a better linkage of the area with the city centre and adjacent neighbourhoods, the need to integrate the ecological assets into the development of the ITP, and the establishment of a dedicated centre of the Innovation and Training Park. In line with the study conclusions, the participants identified strategies such as unsealing of areas for more green space, establishing more accessible and attractive entrance areas and enhancing quality of stay. For example, participants proposed to transform the area in the south into a public park. Regarding available built structures, the hangars as well as the sports areas are identified as important places for public uses. The unique advantage of the topography were emphasised.

Overall, the findings of the spatial analysis and the multi-stakeholder dialogue indicate several strategies for the development of the ITP. In the following section, these strategies are further elaborated and specified.

Figure 7. Multi-stakeholder dialogue: suggestions

**SPATIAL DEVELOPMENT
STRATEGIES**

KEY OBJECTIVES

The proposed spatial strategy focuses on the area's favourable location in close proximity to the city of Prizren and the park's natural surroundings, incorporating influences of both within the area. The core aim is to establish a new use structure that emphasises these qualities and in doing so opens the site to the public to ultimately create a destination for the entire city. While deficits need to be addressed in the key areas of accessibility, cultural programming and climate, it is possible to draw on existing infrastructures and characteristics – also to integrate the historical and spatial dimension of the site into the design. In addition, one key objective is to functionally link the ITP to adjacent areas and incorporate the whole site into the urban fabric of the city.

The aspect of accessibility and mobility is addressed in a concept that improves the entrance, way-finding and orientation in the area. It offers solutions to the challenges of motorised traffic through various mobility offers and allocated parking at the ITP. In terms of climate, the focus is on activating the existing topography and green spaces, while creating robust green and blue infrastructure. The specific character of low-density development with a variety of typologies and a high proportion of green space is a starting point for further development. Successful pioneering uses that meet the strategic vision of a creative economy-oriented Innovation and Training Park should be supported and expanded. Buildings with important uses (e.g. ITP management, event space, public services) should be highlighted at relevant locations in the area. In addition, it is important to create a clearly defined centre that links the various activity clusters in the ITP. The park can be made attractive to visitors by visibly locating anchor uses at relevant positions and defining a central public space as part of the spatial clustering and purposing of the area. The transformed park can – with its new qualities of open space and usable areas – function as a kind of intermediate urban module within Prizren's urban context due to its location between the forested landscape and dense urban space.

FOCUS CATEGORIES

Accessibility and mobility

Improving the mobility structure starts with easier wayfinding and better accessibility. To do so, three access areas have been defined, each equipped with an entry complex, including an entry plaza for meeting and gathering, welcome point (with a recognisable logo as a welcome sign) and a mobility hub. All that serves to provide the information and orientation for visitors as well as an offer for parking and changing to non-motorised modes of transportation.

The individual motorised traffic should be halted at the entry areas by car parks, in order to limit on-site traffic to a minimum, especially on days of public events. The service passage is organised via a loop, with an opportunity for a one-way traffic mode. At the new central square, a fourth hub is created that brings the above-mentioned attributes for mobility and information to the centre of the campus.

Due to the partly long distances and steep topography at the ITP, visitors should receive easy access to shared electric mobility in the form of scooters or bicycles. While individual motorised traffic is kept out of the centre, a public transport line (bus) would be recommended to connect all of the access areas with the central plaza. The network of paths throughout the area is currently primarily dedicated to pedestrian and non-motorised traffic; the south-west axis, which leads to the adjacent residential areas and further into the city centre, is exemplary for this.

- Entrance
- Pathways
- Secondary pedestrian ways
- Crosswalk
- Square
- Bus line/ bus stop
- Carriageways
- Secondary carriageways
- Mobility Hub

CONCEPT: ACCESSIBILITY & MOBILITY

Zoning and programming of the ITP area

The division of certain structural clusters is strongly oriented on the given situation as it is classified in the spatial analysis.

The core is formed by a central public space (the ITP plaza). This existing open space at the conference centre is oversized and not yet well designed; therefore, it is recommended to reframe it by constructing new building edges in the vicinity of the plaza. New development is planned to extend the primary purpose of the central area, such as research and site management, supported by a mobility hub, catering and information services.

To the north of the central plaza, the existing hangars are to be repurposed for small scale manufacturing businesses, creating a "Production Campus", supplemented by food production and communal urban gardening areas on the open spaces.

In the adjacent areas (the sports field and the helipads, the hospital), it is recommended to reuse the existing infrastructure and to expand it respectively in the form of a "Sport and Culture Campus" and a "Health Campus". Being offered for public/semi-public use, both can serve as powerful activating elements for the entire ITP, helping to incorporate the area into the city use canvas.

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Within the entry zones, new buildings provide spatial clarity and guidance, while functioning as welcome points and offering parking space. At the northern main entrance, this spatial structure is continued towards the central plaza by the existing buildings, partially complemented by the new development. Taking into account the successful use of the Autostrada Biennale Hangar for cultural facilities, this area lends itself to a further strengthening of its potential, supported by central location and influence of the neighbouring "Sport and Culture Campus" and "Production Campus".

It is recommended to expand the existing green spaces in the southern areas of the ITP. The scale of the area allows for the creation of several zones with various forms of access and usage. As a valuable amenity for the adjacent residential quarter, a public park with sports and play areas could be established. The eastern part of the area is recommended as a test site for new forms of development, providing future-oriented and flexible work-and-live spaces within an ecological concept.

Figure 9. Concept: zonings and programming

- Central Zone
- Green Zone
- Campus Zone

CONCEPT: ZONING & PROGRAMMING

Climate, nature and landscape

The degree of surface sealing is to be taken into account in replanning the open space structure. Unsealing and renaturation of areas, together with an intensive planting of shadow-giving trees and shrubbery, could improve the climatic quality of the ITP.

Rows of trees should be planted along all the pathways and roads on the campus to improve the quality of pedestrian circulation by providing shade. This should be also considered at all locations and public spaces intended for lingering, such as meeting points, areas for catering or places with a panoramic view over the city. Larger sealed areas (such as the entry zones and the central plaza), should be designed with special attention to air circulation and, if possible, include artificial water elements such as water playgrounds and fountains.

It is recommended to use the existing system of drainage ditches for the integration of watercourses. In addition to their role of cooling the area in the hot summer months, they can enhance aesthetic qualities and afford the area a playful character. The waterway system is to be complemented by larger open areas for water infiltration and evaporation at suitable locations, supporting microclimate and plant diversity.

Many and various qualities of the heterogeneous open space are to be used in order to diversify the spatial purposes with minimum necessary enhancements. The flat northern area provides plenty of suitable ground for urban agriculture, the bosky southeast hills offer great amenity as a park for the adjacent residential area. The existing sports infrastructure next to the national motorway is planned as a welcoming public area allowing loud activities.

- Green roofs
- Microclimate management
- Sealed areas reduction
- Green areas
- Woodland areas
- Urban gardening
- Tree alleys
- Rainwater system

Micro climate management
 Vapor spriclers
 Shadow
 Water elements/play

Playfields

Sitting

Mobile Sitting

Green Buffer

Water management
 Rain water collection/reuse
 Green/ Energy roofs

Mobile Sitting

Water Play

Health Garden

Garden

Urban Gardening

Sitting

Community Garden

Kurilat Park

Future Village

Water Play

CONCEPT: CLIMATE, NATURE & LANDSCAPE

STRUCTURAL MAP

The following map sums up the above-mentioned strategies, grouped in three key themes (mobility, programming, climate), as a basis for further discussion, planning and detailing.

Main and secondary access points are allocated in the map as well as the pathway network and the motorised-traffic dedicated transit loop with a public bus line. The depicted zoning includes primary functionality of each cluster as well as suggested development fields, important spatial edges and supporting service allocation (mobility hubs, info points). The climate layer includes important greening measures such as tree rows and areas for larger forest planting, possible locations for the infiltration areas and suggested zones for food production and gardening.

Figure 11. Structural map

CONCEPT: STRUCTURAL MAP

**STRATEGIC
IMPLEMENTATION
PROCESS**

PHASES OF DEVELOPMENT

It is apparent that the conclusive development of the area will take a long time and that the transformation process of the ITP must be implemented in certain temporal and functional steps.

First and foremost, parts of the area should be made more accessible and usable by interested visitors and the general public. The sports campus and the green areas to the southeast are particularly suitable for this. These areas can be activated with low-threshold measures and temporal intervention projects, making the park partly available for the residents of the adjacent neighbourhoods. In the next phase, the focus should be on the formation of an articulated centre from where further impulses will emanate to other parts of the ITP. Within this step, it is necessary to define building edges and formulate the general layout and the atmosphere of the space and bring centrally located buildings into active use. Subsequently, the peripheral areas should be addressed individually or in parallel, taking into account their individual characteristics.

Figure 12. Development steps

PROCESS DESIGN

These above-described development stages come in accordance with certain implementation strategies. Various measures that were unfolded in the spatial strategy section are to be planned in parallel to the three development steps.

For pilot projects, one can rely on short-term and low-threshold measures, such as the implementation of interim uses at carefully selected key locations, the activation of at least one entrance situation and part of the sports campus, and the unsealing of key areas. Further steps include the more thorough and intensive enhancement of green structures and the water management system as well as works on topography and the construction of the mobility hubs for each focus area. Finally, the refurbishment of the central area and the establishment of permanent users and tenants should lay the foundation for all further economic and spatial development of the Innovation and Training Park Prizren in the future.

Figure 13. Process diagram

ACTIVATION MEASURES AND INTERVENTIONS

Activation interventions can draw on experience from the field of tactical urbanism. They are particularly suitable for boosting the potential of areas during the very first development phase and attract potential users and tenants of the ITP. Their key characteristics are easy production and implementation, low costs and temporal existence. Interventions are to be located on spots, which can unfold existing amenities of the space for visitors and positively introduce it to the general public.

The entrance areas hold a key role in the strategy to improve access and mobility. As a first step, the activities should focus on one entry zone, to which attention could be drawn by a high tower-like installation with recognisable design. Especially in contrast to the previous repellent external appearance of the area, the intervention could create an inviting and attractive atmosphere at the entrance. It could offer information about the ongoing development of the ITP and give orientation to the site and an overview of current activities and interventions. Local communities may be involved in participatory projects to enhance the entry area as the interactive edge between the ITP and the adjacent neighbourhood.

Temporary measures can also be used to activate larger areas of the site. Movable planters, containers, mobile stages, temporary sport and play elements may be used to quickly generate new life in the areas without extensive construction. It is essential to develop high quality public spaces, as well as designated areas for lunch breaks, meetings, networking and information exchange. This is crucial to strengthen the local ecosystem and foster collaborations and networking between the different users and tenants of the ITP on a spatial level. (Cultural) programming and participatory activities could be organised by single tenants based on their area of business and activity or in collaboration with the central ITP management for overarching public events.

Low-maintenance ground plantation and partial unsealing of surfaces may contribute to the strategy regarding the microclimate. Here, positive effects can be reached by additionally converting some areas to communal gardening. It is also important to provide sheltered and shaded areas and seating at all key locations and along main fluxes.

Figure 14. Activating

Figure 15. Measures map

CONCEPT: MEASURES MAP

**FOCUS AREAS OF SPATIAL
DEVELOPMENT**

The primary spatial programmatic and design focus lies on two core areas of the ITP, the central square and the main entrance area. Both require a dedicated purpose and careful detailed planning to ensure an attractive public image and a successful sustainable spatial transformation and development of the entire park.

In line with the three main strategic objectives, the ITP should be open and accessible to all target groups and offer a variety of different activities and services to provide a wide range of uses and economic development opportunities. Physical and spatial qualities such as well-maintained surfaces, absence of obstacles and appropriate inclinations are equally essential. In both focus areas, all necessary services are to be combined in one building in the form of a mobility hub, providing information and orientation, offering parking and other mobility services as well as additional functionality such as catering and office space or maintenance rooms. Adjacent open areas are to enable user-friendly space for meeting and gathering, where comfortable shadowed seating is of foremost importance.

Figure 16. Localisation map

CENTRAL ITP PLAZA

Presenting the central plaza as the heart of the ITP, the proposed layout of the space suggests defining building edges by clearing representational facades of auxiliary elements and constructing new edges – a mobility hub at the northern edge and an addition to the existing building on the western one. The edges are to be designed in a manner of active facades with preferably glass surfaces, inviting entrances and a variety of ground-floor uses. The inconvenient inclination of the area is to be reshaped in order to enhance accessibility, which can be done by forming terraces and introducing appropriate ramps.

Functional zoning advocates for a free space, intended for larger gatherings and events. At times it can be activated by movable furniture and design elements that can be easily cleared when needed. Surface materials and other design solutions should not interfere with the functionality dictated by the planned uses. The counterpart to the open event space is a raised, terraced area that offers sheltered comfort for longer stays. More inviting surfaces and sitting opportunities are desired here, as well as various elements providing shade and introducing playfulness to the area.

Figure 17. Building organisation at Central ITP Plaza

CONCEPT: CENTRAL ITP PLAZA

ENTRY ZONE

A comfortable and attractive arrival experience and visitor introduction to the park should be ensured by the recommended layout for the main entry zone.

Therefore, the chosen entrance should be visible and accessible from the National Motorway M25 in the immediate vicinity of a public transport stop and a pedestrian crossing. A welcome sign clearly marking the entrance for both pedestrians and vehicles should be positioned such that it is visible from afar. In order to ensure safe and easy access for all groups of visitors, different mobility modes are divided, offering clear wayfinding for pedestrians as well as comprehensible navigation for motorised vehicles, including signage for parking and further guidance. The gateway role of the entry zone is supported by its border location between two structural clusters – Sport Campus and Production Campus – introducing the ITP programmatic variety and offering direct access for target users. In that sense, the public spaces could have a certain flexibility of use and thus become a showcase for the entire park. Here, suitable spaces can be used for public events and exhibitions, such as the site of the Autostrada Biennale. Other areas can also be used for participatory urban gardening projects and gastronomic offerings that also take into account the needs of the surrounding neighbourhoods of the ITP.

Figure 18. Building organisation in the entry zone

CONCEPT: ENTRY ZONE

CONCLUSION

The goal of the study was to develop an urban design strategy for the former KFOR military camp, currently being transformed into an Innovation and Training Park. Overall, the study demonstrates the importance of strategic planning and an approach towards user-oriented development to successfully integrate the site into the urban fabric. The findings provide a framework for further planning and development, which can contribute to the ongoing sustainable transformation of the area and help a local innovation ecosystem to flourish.

A combination of individual structural and design measures implemented in an iterative process of low-threshold interventions in cooperation with the tenants and users of the ITP is intended to pave the way for a holistic development of the ITP. The site's unique structure and urban location offer excellent starting points, so that these tailor-made and carefully developed measures can work towards a spatial structural change that reverberates beyond the park's boundaries. The approach of producing spaces experimentally in participation with various stakeholders can provide important indications for concrete spatial needs and promote the development of an active user-tenant network.

Landscape planning measures contribute greatly to the quality of a stay at the ITP; while new mobility offers will ensure accessibility and exchange, with the entrance and mobility hubs providing orientation and creating accessibility.

Opening up the former military site to the public is a great opportunity for the development of the ITP and can serve as a catalyst for the entire city.

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PHOTOS

All following photos have been accessed on February 9th, 2023.

Cover image by Tim Hüfner on Unsplash

Picture 01) <https://jna-sfrj.forumbo.net/11661-prizren-1973-1974-golo-jaje-15-mptad-i-vp-9650-52>

Picture 02) https://de.m.wikipedia.org/wiki/Datei:Camp_Prizren_2002-03-21_Blue_Residence.jpg
Source: Rolling Bone

Picture 03) <https://www.dbwv.de/aktuelle-themen/einsatz-aktuell/beitrag/nach-fast-20-jahren-abzug-aus-prizren> – Source: dpa

Picture 04) https://www.gea.de/welt/politik_artikel,-nächster-schritt-zum-frieden-im-kosovo-_arid,6067859.html – Source: Bundeswehr

Picture 05) <https://itp-prizren.com/> – Source: Innovation and Training Park (ITP) Prizren

Picture 06 – 11) Source: Christian Grauvogel, private

Picture 12) <https://kollektivplusx.de/hal-lei-rad-weg> – Source: Kollektiv Plus X

Picture 13) <https://www.koer.or.at/projekte/add-on-20-hoehenmeter> – Source: Michael Nagl

Picture 14) <https://atelier-loidl.de/en/gleisdreieck-nach-10-jahren> – Source: Leonard Grosch

Picture 14) <https://cities-today.com/the-tactical-urbanism-transforming-milans-streets> – Source: City of Milan

Picture 16) <https://www.artmagazine.cc/content18991.html> – Source: Artmagazine

Picture 17) <https://www.pinterest.de/pin/23081016815853250> – Source: Build a Better Burb

Picture 18) <https://dirtstudio.com/ee/work/core-city-park> – Source: Prince Concepts

ANNEX

- Green space
- Sealed surfaces
- Water channels
- Buildings

INVENTORY OF LANDSCAPE

- Important buildings
- Important spatial edges

INVENTORY OF BUILT STRUCTURE

- Entrance/ traffic knot
- Main car routes ITP
- M25
- Traffic area
- Fences
- Barrier for pedestrians
- Pedestrian movements

INVENTORY OF ACCESSIBILITY

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